

Limbal conjunctival papilloma vs carcinoma in situ: a case report

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Clinical Image

A 67-year-old female patient with no previous history of conjunctival papilloma presented with a conjunctival lesion that had been appearing for 6 months and was increasing in size, prompting a visit to the emergency room. Ophthalmological examination revealed visual acuity of 6/10 in both eyes, and examination of the conjunctiva of the right eye revealed a well-defined whitish limbal lesion (Figure 1). The lesion was suggestive of carcinoma in situ. A biopsy was taken and histological examination showed epithelial hyperplasia in favor of a papilloma; the patient underwent complete excision and local treatment with mitomycin.

Limbal papilloma is a typically benign lesion, frequently seen in older adults. These lesions may extend centrally to the cornea or laterally to the conjunctiva [1-2]. In our patient, the location and age were typical, but the appearance is atypical: a whitish, budding lesion.

Figure 1: image showing the appearance of the lesion

Reference

[1] Chang T, Chapman B, Heathcote JG. Inverted mucoepidermoid papilloma of the conjunctiva. *Can J Ophthalmol.* 1993 Jun;28(4):184-6. PMID: 8393730.

[2] Ramberg I, Sjö NC, Bonde JH, Heegaard S. Inverted papilloma of the conjunctiva. *BMJ Open Ophthalmol.* 2019 Feb 28;4(1):e000193. doi: 10.1136/bmjophth-2018-000193. PMID: 30997398; PMCID: PMC6440594.